

ON TITRATION OF SODIUM HYPONITRITE WITH MINERAL ACIDS

BY T. M. OZA, N. L. DIPALI AND V. T. OZA

It is known that aqueous solutions of sodium hyponitrite decompose slowly into N_2O and $NaOH$, gradually in the cold, and rapidly when heated (cf. Divers, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 75, 95). Further, aqueous solutions of hyponitrous acid decompose into H_2O and N_2O rapidly at and above 25° , and slowly at 0° (cf. Hantzsch and Kauffmann, *Ber.*, 1896 29, 317). It would therefore appear that decomposition of solutions of sodium hyponitrite may be the result of the hydrolysis of the salt into sodium hydroxide and hyponitrous acid. No nitrite or nitrate has been detected in the aqueous solutions (cf. Partington and Shah, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2071). It thus appeared interesting if sodium hyponitrite could be determined simply by titrating its freshly made solution with a standard acid. The isosterism of carbon dioxide and nitrous oxide shows that sodium hyponitrite (Na_2O , N_2O) might behave like sodium carbonate (Na_2O , CO_2).

Sodium hyponitrite was prepared as by Oza (this *Journal*, 1944, 21, 71). It contained no nitrite or carbonate and on analysis it gave the following results: (i) 1.9082 g. (hydrated) gave 1.0322 g. on complete dehydration. The loss corresponds to 91.85 g. for $Na_2N_2O_2$; (ii) 0.0119 g. (anhydrous substance) gave 0.0130 g. $NaCl$ and 0.014 g. requires 5.85 c.c. of 0.04493N-KCNS (Oza and Walawalkar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc., Ind. & News Ed.*, 1946, 9, 57). (Found: Na , 43.1; N_2O_2 %, 56.2. Calc. for $Na_2N_2O_2$: Na , 43.4; N_2O_2 %, 56.6 per cent).

The results of titration at room temperature with 0.1N- HNO_3 , are shown in Table I, while Table II contains results of similar experiments at the temperature of ice. Table III contains results of the experiments with 0.101N- HCl in the ice-cold solution. In the experiments, a weighed quantity of the anhydrous salt is added to 20 c.c. of water and immediately titrated. When titrated in the ice-cold solution, ice-cold water is used and the flask is held in the ice cold bath. At room temperature, a deceptive end-point is witnessed with phenolphthalein, but this is not so at the temperature of ice when the titration reading is exactly half as much as with methyl orange. The cause of the deceptive end-point with phenolphthalein, at room temperature, may lie in the relative instability of the hydro-hyponitrite formed.

TABLE I

Titration of $Na_2N_2O_2$ with standard HNO_3 at room temperature.

$Na_2N_2O_2$ taken.	Reading with 0.1013N- HNO_3 with		Percentage $Na_2N_2O_2$ found with	
	Phenolphthalein.	Methyl orange.	Phenolphthalein.	Methyl orange.
0.0222 g.	2.5 c.c.	4.25 c.c.	60.4	102.7
0.0338	3.7	6.3	58.7	100.0
0.0266	2.95	4.95	59.5	99.8
0.0342	3.80	6.45	59.6	101.1
0.0193	2.15	3.55	59.1	99.3

TABLE II

Titration of Na₂N₂O₂ with 0.1N-HNO₃ at 0°.

Na ₂ N ₂ O ₂ taken.	Reading with		Percentage Na ₂ N ₂ O ₂ found with	
	Phenolphthalein.	Methyl orange.	Phenolphthalein	Methyl orange.
0.0286 g.	2.75 c.c.	5.5 c.c.	50.95	101.6
0.0226	2.15	4.3	50.42	100.8
0.0365	3.55	7.0	51.7	102.0
0.0346	3.30	6.55	50.55	100.3

TABLE III

Titration of Na₂N₂O₂ with 0.101N- HCl at 0°.

Na ₂ N ₂ O ₂ taken.	Reading with		Percentage Na ₂ N ₂ O ₂ found with	
	Phenolphthalein.	Methyl orange.	Phenolphthalein.	Methyl orange.
0.0400 g.	3.9 c.c.	3.9 c.c.	51.2	102.4
0.0545	5.1	5.0	50.0	99.3

TABLE IV

Titration of mixtures of Na₂N₂O₂ and NaOH with 0.101N HCl at 0°.

Na ₂ N ₂ O ₂ taken.	Reading with		HCl ≡ of	HCl required with		Na ₂ N ₂ O ₂ Calc.
	Phenolphthalein.	Methyl orange.	NaOH taken.	Phenolphthalein.	Methyl orange.	
0.0101 g.	10.3 c.c.	0.95 c.c.	9.4 c.c.	0.90 c.c.	0.95 c.c.	0.0102 g.
0.0254	11.7	2.30	"	2.30	2.3	0.0253
0.0420	13.4	4.00	"	4.00	4.00	0.0424
0.0500	14.1	4.60	"	4.70	4.60	0.0499
0.0520	14.7	4.90	"	4.90	4.90	0.0524
0.0600	16.8	5.6	"	5.60	5.6	0.0599

The analogy between the carbonate and hyponitrite of sodium seems close for, mixtures of the hydroxide and hyponitrite could be titrated to determine the amounts of the two. The titration must be conducted at 0°. The results shown in Table IV have been obtained by titrating such mixtures, taking a measured volume of the hydroxide in a conical flask, cooling the solution and adding an accurately weighed quantity of the hyponitrite.